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3 **Micromechanics of Hydro-Thermo-Mechanical Processes in Rock Accounting**
4 **for Thermal Convection**

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10 **Abstract**

11 This paper presents the results of a comprehensive micromechanical study to improve the
12 understanding of the coupled hydro-thermo-mechanical (HTM) processes during injection of
13 pressurized cold fluid in permeable hot rock. At the microscopic level, it is expected that fluid-
14 flow-induced convective temperature changes in the voids will dominate the conductive heat flow
15 from grain to grain. However, the coupled interactions between fluid flow, thermal convection and
16 conduction, and the resulting changes in local permeability due to thermo-poro-elastic stresses at
17 the grain scale remain poorly understood. Moreover, almost all previous studies at large scale have
18 only focused on thermal conduction. The study used the Discrete Element Method (DEM)
19 modified to account for convective heat transport to model the particulate interactions between
20 rock grains, and between rock deformation, fluid pressure and temperature. The results indicate
21 that wellbore pressure, provided it is less than the fracturing threshold, has less significant role in
22 rock cooling around the wellbore, which is governed predominately by rock permeability, as
23 previously thought. Different applied flow rates into the wellbore resulted in low and high wellbore
24 pressures at short times in the absence of rock fracturing. As expected, convective heat transport
25 dominated over conduction, resulting in a cooled ring around the wellbore without significant
26 thermal gradient zone due to conductive heat flow. As the fluid infiltrates and cools down the rock,
27 preferential fluid flow paths occur as fingering instabilities that are oriented towards the minimum
28 principal horizontal stress even in the absence of initial local anisotropic porosity variations.

29

30 Keywords: Discrete Element Method, convective-conductive heat flow, hot dry rock, rock
31 permeability, wellbore pressure

32 **1. Introduction**

33 This paper investigates the microscopic coupled hydro-thermo-mechanical (HTM) processes in
34 permeable hot rock due to cold fluid pressurization from a wellbore under high stress and high
35 temperature conditions. Although much effort has been devoted towards the modeling of the
36 coupled processes in rock at the reservoir and wellbore scales, relatively little effort has been
37 devoted to the understanding HTM couplings and the resulting local rock permeability changes at
38 the microscale. At the local microscale, convective heat transfer due to flow of a fluid at different
39 temperature from the rock matrix is expected to dominate over thermal conduction from grain to
40 grain. This temperature change, together with the fluid pressures, will induce thermo-poroelastic
41 stress changes at the grains and contacts thereby affecting local permeability, and eventually fluid
42 pressures and temperatures. An improved understanding of heat flow and transport, particularly
43 any instabilities and local induced permeability changes, are important in different fields such as
44 enhanced geothermal systems (EGS), CO₂ geological sequestration, oil and gas production,
45 contaminant disposal, and nuclear waste storage. In many geo-energy and geo-environmental
46 applications, rock temperatures can reach up to 250 °C or higher. Pressurized cold fluid pumped
47 through a wellbore in rocks at elevated temperatures will result in significant temperature
48 differences between the fluid and the rock and induce spatial and temporal changes of the thermo-
49 mechanical stress state locally. The fundamental HTM processes in the rock are coupled. First,
50 fluid flow field affects the temperature due to convection and vice versa due to temperature-
51 dependent fluid properties. Second, fluid pressure and temperature affect rock mechanical
52 response, with repercussions to fracturing processes and long-term reservoir behavior. Third, rock
53 mechanical response can affect fluid pressures and permeability of the rock mass. The processes
54 are fully coupled as hydro-thermal response affects mechanical response and vice versa (Gutierrez
55 and Lewis 2002).

56 The importance of hydro-thermo-mechanical coupling effects in rocks has been highlighted by
57 many researchers who have carried out studies numerically and experimentally. Numerical
58 methods included the Finite Element Method (FEM), integral methods, boundary element
59 methods, hybrid continuum methods combined with fluid flow solved over discrete fractures, and
60 Discrete Element Method (DEM) (Bower and Zyvoloski 1997; Geiger and Emmanuel 2010;

61 Ghassemi 2012; Ghassemi et al. 2008; Kolditz and Clauser 1998; McDermott et al. 2009; Tomac
62 2014; Tomac 2007; (Ingrid Tomac and Gutierrez 2015; Ingrid Tomac and Gutierrez 2016; Wang
63 and Dusseault 2003). Experimental and field data were used to support modeling efforts (Rutqvist
64 et al. 2008; Yong and Wang 1980; Frash et al. 2014). In hot dry rock geothermal reservoirs, fluid-
65 rock interactions govern the rock mass hydro-thermo-mechanical behavior at large scale, and
66 arbitrary oriented fractures can cause the commonly used heat transfer approaches to
67 underestimate hot water production (Hicks et al. 1966). For an illustration, the thermal influence
68 on the permeability of an EGS study at the reservoir scale was found to be significant at an
69 intermediate time scale of one month (Taron and Elsworth 2009). In addition, preferential fluid
70 flow paths and shortcuts may develop in rock, depending on the mechanical and thermal stress
71 releases during intense exploitation of geothermal systems (McDermott et al. 2006). Coupled
72 analysis of hydro-thermo-mechanical and chemical rock behavior in undrained finite difference
73 model coupled with fluid flow model also showed that thermal loading of rock may lead to an
74 irreversible reduction in flow path aperture and stress (Taron and Elsworth 2009; Taron et al.
75 2009). Existing fractures in rock mass may dilate or contract as a result of fluctuations in fluid
76 pressure or thermo-mechanical stress field during production (McDermott et al. 2009; Rutqvist et
77 al. 2002). Heat flow and transport was considered through a simplified fracture geometry using
78 hybrid numerical and analytical approaches where the fracture is discretely spatially fixed and
79 analytical heat diffusion solution was used for the rock matrix (McDermott et al. 2009). Thermo-
80 poroelastic finite element model enabled studying the response of a natural fractured system to
81 cold fluid injection at a reservoir scale (Koh et al. 2011). Thermal tensile stresses at the crack tip
82 are induced by cold water flow, causing natural fractures to open and increase reservoir
83 permeability within the zone of cooling (Koh et al. 2011). In a fractured geologic media, it is
84 unclear if non-Fourier heat flow occurs and whether it can be modeled by an advection-diffusion
85 equation (Geiger and Emmanuel 2010). Non-Fourier heat transfer arises also due to heterogeneities
86 present at different spatial scales, including fractures and lithological and petrographic variations,
87 as studied with the Continuous Time Random Walk (CTRW) model (Berkowitz et al. 2006). At a
88 small model scale, the transient conductive heat flow in granite provided evidence of spatial and
89 temporal redistribution of the thermal field around the borehole (Gibb et al. 2008). The propagating
90 thermal disturbance affected the fluid flow pressure gradients in jointed rock mass in a one-
91 dimensional conductive-advective two-phase continuum study (Elsworth 1989). Hydrothermal

92 convection has been studied in porous media including rocks experimentally and numerically.
93 Mass transport of heat by deeper underground waterflow through permeable rock and in faults is
94 especially difficult to evaluate because of irregularities in porosity and permeability of the rock,
95 as well as irregularities in the hydrodynamics, convection, mass transport of heat, and thermal
96 conduction of the water (Robertson, 1988).

97 The fundamental coupled convective-conductive heat flow and transport in granular and
98 porous medial has not yet been fully addressed and understood. Micro-mechanical modeling of
99 the HTM processes around wellbores using the Discrete Element Method (DEM) can enable a
100 better understanding of the coupled processes involved. DEM dynamically updates rock
101 permeability at the microscale at time step due to deformations from pore pressure and temperature
102 changes. Fluid flow paths dynamically open or close, widen or narrow, which is a step forward
103 from the stochastic-deterministic fracture networks and CTRW models. Convective-conductive
104 heat flow and transport in rocks is complicated due to the extremely different length scales of both
105 processes. The discretization over relatively small particle size typical for DEM model improves
106 the accuracy of the solution. DEM has recently been significantly improved by the introduction of
107 convective heat transport for simulating transient heat energy exchange between fluid in motion
108 and rock by Tomac and Gutierrez (2015). This type of problem cannot be handled using analytical
109 solutions. Intrusion of cold fluid in the low permeability hot dry rock matrix causes thermal strains
110 accompanied with forming and widening of preferential fluid flow paths and instabilities, which
111 in return enables more fluid to infiltrate the rock matrix. This study visualizes and numerically
112 evaluates different scenarios of heat and fluid infiltration in rock around wellbore in a small sample
113 that affect HTM response.

114 **2. Methodology**

115 The coupled DEM HTM model combines transient effects of conductive and convective heat flow
116 and transport is implemented in the PFC^{2D} software (Tomac and Gutierrez 2015). The mechanical
117 behavior of the model of synthetic porous rock matrix is coupled with explicit transient Newtonian
118 fluid flow through deformable rock matrix or designated channels and heat flow and transport. The
119 combined heat flow and transport model aims to capture the complete thermal energy migration
120 (without radiation) through permeable solid filled with flowing fluid with initially non-uniform
121 thermal distribution. Ultimately, the spatial discretization that is unique for DEM method enables
122 simulations of arbitrary oriented single and interconnected fluid channels through the solid. The

123 temporal evolution of preferential fluid path geometry in permeable rock matrix is coupled with
124 the redistribution of thermal and mechanical stress fields. Local thermal equilibrium between fluid
125 and rock is assumed during the simulation during each time step, which is reasonable given the
126 very small element sizes used to discretize the geometries.

127

128 *2.1 Thermal Conduction*

129 The heat conduction between contacting DEM particles that defines the transient flow of
130 thermal energy through the model from initially non-uniform spatial distribution is a standard
131 feature in DEM. However, the heat convective flow, which occurs during fluid migration through
132 synthetic rock matrix, has been only recently implemented and coupled with conduction by authors
133 (Tomac and Gutierrez 2015 and 2016). The convective-conductive heat flow and transport is
134 formulated using lumped capacitance method which includes the justification of the local
135 equilibrium assumption and was verified against rock experiments in Tomac and Gutierrez (2015).

136 Heat conduction for a continuum follows Fourier's law that describes the relation between the
137 heat-flux vector q_i and the temperature gradient $\partial T / \partial x_j$ as:

$$q_i = -k_{i,j} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} \quad (1)$$

138 where $k_{i,j}$ is the thermal conductivity tensor [W/mK]. The transient heat conduction equation for a
139 continuum under assumption that strain changes play a negligible role in influencing the
140 temperature is:

$$-\frac{\partial q_i}{\partial x_i} + q_v = \rho C_v \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad (2)$$

141 where $\partial q_i / \partial x_i$ represents the heat-flux gradient, q_v is the volumetric heat source/sink intensity or
142 power density [W/m²], ρ is the mass density, C_v is the specific heat at constant volume [J/kg K], T
143 is the temperature [K] and t is time. Fig. 1 shows the thermal DEM discretization with a network
144 of "heat reservoirs" at the center of particles mass interconnected with "thermal pipes" passing via
145 contacts between particles.

146 Parameters for the conductive heat flow equation related to each thermal reservoir are the
 147 temperature T , the mass m , the volume V , the specific heat at constant volume C_v , and the
 148 coefficient of linear thermal expansion, α_t . Associated with each thermal pipe are the heat energy
 149 Q and the thermal resistance η . The heat outflow per unit volume is given by divergence of q_i . The
 150 average value of the divergence of q_i in the thermal reservoir is defined by:

$$\nabla \cdot q_i = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \left(\frac{\partial q_i}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial y_i} + \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial z_i} \right) dV \quad (3)$$

151 where q_i is the heat-flux vector at the i -th reservoir. The volume integral can be replaced with
 152 surface integral using Gauss-Ostrogradsky's divergence theorem. Integrating the field's
 153 divergence over the interior of the single thermal reservoir equals the integral of the vector field
 154 over the thermal reservoir's boundary. The heat flow per unit volume of particle is obtained from
 155 Eq. (3) as:

$$\nabla \cdot q_i = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \left(\frac{\partial q_i}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial y_i} + \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial z_i} \right) dV = \frac{1}{V} \int_S q_i n_i dS = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{p=1}^N q_i^p n_i^p \Delta S^p = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{p=1}^N Q^p \quad (4)$$

156 where q_i is the heat-flux vector at the i -th reservoir, V is the thermal reservoir control volume, S is
 157 the surface of the control volume, n_i is the outward unit normal vector of the surface, p denotes
 158 thermal pipe, N is the number of thermal pipes for each control volume and Q^p is the heat energy
 159 in the thermal pipe p that is flowing out of the thermal reservoir. The heat conduction equation for
 160 a single thermal reservoir is obtained by substitution of Eq. (4) into Eq. (2):

$$-\sum_{p=1}^N Q^p + Q^v = m C_v \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad (5)$$

161 where Q^v is the heat-source intensity, m is the thermal mass and C_v is the specific heat at constant
 162 volume. Each thermal pipe is regarded as a one-dimensional object with a thermal resistance per
 163 unit length of η , then the thermal energy is given by:

$$Q^p = -\frac{\Delta T}{\eta L} \quad (6)$$

164 where ΔT is the temperature difference between the two thermal reservoirs at each end of the
 165 thermal pipe, and L is the thermal pipe length. The thermal resistance per unit length parameter η
 166 is verified towards the known thermal conductivity tensor of the material, $k_{i,j}$. The verification

167 procedure includes varying the parameter η and testing the DEM assembly heat flow until the
 168 thermally isotropic material with a mean macroscopic conductivity $k_{i,j}$ is obtained. Variations of
 169 the heat flow properties within the model are not permitted in the current formulation and are left
 170 for the future model development.

171 The transient conductive heat flow is numerically discretized in DEM using the explicit finite
 172 difference equation (FDE). Numerical stability and convergence of the explicit FDE depends on
 173 conditions that are related to the time-step size and other parameters. In DEM, numerical stability
 174 and convergence are satisfied if the time-step is smaller than (Cundall 2004):

$$\Delta t < \frac{mC_v}{\sum \frac{1}{\eta L}} \quad (7)$$

175 2.2 Thermo-Mechanical Coupling

176 The stress tensor of the DEM assembly spatially evolves during the time-stepping procedure.
 177 Stress changes consist of mechanical and thermal components. The thermal stress component is a
 178 consequence of temperature-induced strains in DEM, which, particularly, arise due to thermal
 179 volumetric deformation of particles and contact bonds. The temperature-induced particle radius
 180 change is:

$$\Delta R = \alpha R \Delta T \quad (8)$$

181 where R is the particle radius, α is the particle coefficient of linear thermal expansion and ΔT is
 182 the temperature change. If parallel bond is present at the particle contact associated with a pipe
 183 (Cundall 2004), then the thermal volumetric deformation of the bond material is accounted for by
 184 assuming that only the normal component of the force vector carried by the bond will be affected
 185 by the temperature change. The bond length, \bar{L} changes with the normal component of the bond
 186 force vector as:

$$\Delta F^n = \bar{k}^n A \Delta U^n = \bar{k}^n A (\bar{\alpha} \bar{L} \Delta T) \quad (9)$$

187 where \bar{k}^n is the bond normal stiffness, A is the area of the bond cross-section, $\bar{\alpha}$ is the expansion
 188 coefficient of the bond material, and ΔT is the temperature increment (taken equal to the average
 189 temperature change of the two particles at the ends of the pipe associated with the bond).

190 Fluid flows through a system of interconnected channels of coherent particle assembly with
 191 strong pressure gradients, where the fluid and the heat convective flow are implemented in PFC^{2D}
 192 using PFC's built-in FISH programming language. The fluid flow scheme has a limitation to model
 193 only the solid or quasi-solid materials where particles do not significantly spatially rearrange
 194 during the calculation. Fig. 2 shows the fluid flow network built upon bonded DEM particles in
 195 synthetic rock mass. In Fig. 2, fluid channels are placed at particle contacts, and fluid reservoirs
 196 connect fluid channels. Fluid reservoirs are introduced for transient fluid flow modeling and the
 197 conservation of mass.

198 The aperture of a fluid channel is proportional to the normal displacement at corresponding
 199 contact, and the fluid reservoir volumes that are related to the sizes of surrounding channels.
 200 Pressures are stored in fluid reservoirs and are updated during the fluid calculation, and act on the
 201 surrounding particles as equivalent body forces. The micro-permeability of the DEM specimen is
 202 obtained by performing tests which ensure that the sample matches the required permeability of
 203 the realistic material. Additional tests can be also done to develop an evolution law for micro-
 204 permeability as a function of strain. In the numerical sense, the fluid flow through a network of
 205 channels and reservoirs is superimposed to the DEM particle assembly finite difference scheme.
 206 The fluid flow rate, q_f , in a fluid channel is calculated using the parallel plate flow. It is assumed
 207 that each contact has residual initial fluid channel aperture, d_0 , when the normal contact force is at
 208 its prescribed residual value. The increase in normal load decreases the apparent fluid channel
 209 aperture in the case of compressive normal contact force:

$$d = \frac{d_0 F_0}{F + F_0} \quad (10)$$

210 where F is the value of normal contact force and F_0 is its residual value at d_0 . For the case of tensile
 211 normal contact force:

$$d = d_0 + za \quad (11)$$

212 where z is arbitrary chosen dimensionless multiplier which can be set different from unity for
 213 calibration purposes, and a is the physical distance between two particle contacts. The increase in
 214 fluid pressure in a fluid reservoir is:

$$\Delta P = \frac{K_f}{V_d} (\Sigma q_f \Delta t - \Delta V_d) \quad (12)$$

215 where K_f is the fluid bulk modulus, V_d is the apparent volume of the fluid, q_f is the fluid flow rate
 216 and Δt is the time step. Finally, it is assumed that the fluid flow through a fluid channel is localized
 217 at the corresponding contact, and the pressure region of the fluid reservoir is uniform, leading to
 218 the tractions that are independent of the path around the fluid reservoir. For the polygonal path that
 219 joins the contacts which surround the fluid reservoir, the force vector F_i on a particle is:

$$F_i = P n_i b \quad (13)$$

220 where n_i is the unit normal vector of the line joining the two contact points on the particle and b is
 221 the length of the line. Consequently, the time-stepping procedure in DEM resolves model
 222 mechanical response using all the forces imposed on each DEM particle.

223 *2.3 Thermal Convection*

224 Heat exchange between solid phase and fluid in channels occurs simultaneously with fluid flow
 225 driven by pressure gradients in fluid channels which exist between particles. Parallel plate flow
 226 solution is introduced in the numerical scheme for fluid and heat flow at fluid channel. While the
 227 fluid flow scheme and the conductive heat flow scheme already existed as standard in PFC
 228 package, the coupled convective-conductive heat flow and transport was introduced in DEM by
 229 the authors in the previous publication (Tomac and Gutierrez 2015). Eq. (14) below gives the heat
 230 convection approximation for the laminar fluid flow in a channel between two parallel plates.
 231 Mean fluid velocity and temperature parameters are introduced for the flow between two parallel
 232 plates:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{T_s(x) - T(r, x)}{T_s(x) - T_m(x)} \right]_{fd,t} = 0 \quad (14)$$

233 where x is the axial channel dimension, $T_s(x)$ is the channel surface temperature at a position x ,
 234 $T_m(x)$ is the mean fluid temperature at a position x , and $T(r, x)$ is the fluid temperature at a position
 235 x and distance r from the center of the channel in y direction perpendicular to x . Fig. 3 shows the
 236 mean temperature and surface temperature with advection along the channel of length L . Eq. (14)
 237 assumes conductive heat flow from the channel boundary into the fluid and vice versa, while
 238 conductive heat flow in the fluid along the channel lengths is neglected (i.e., heat convection is
 239 one-dimensional along the lengths of the channels only). The conductive heat flow along the
 240 channel can be neglected by observing the Peclet number. The relative significance of convective

241 and conductive heat transfers in fluid during channel flow can be estimated by checking the value
 242 of the Peclet number, Pe :

$$Pe = \frac{\rho^f v C_p L}{\lambda^f} \quad (15)$$

243 where ρ^f is the fluid density, v is the fluid velocity, C_p is the fluid specific heat at a constant
 244 pressure, L is the fluid channel length and λ^f is the fluid thermal conductivity. For $Pe > 1$ fluid
 245 convection dominates over conduction, and for $Pe \gg 1$ the conduction parallel to the fluid flow can
 246 be neglected (Patankar 1980). Potential and kinetic particle energy changes are negligible, and the
 247 fluid and particle specific heat capacities do not change. The amount of heat transferred from the
 248 host material to the fluid and vice versa over a given time-step equals to the amount of heat
 249 extracted from the particle at the end of the time-step. Because two particles adjacent to the fluid
 250 channel change temperature due to both convection and conduction through the granular assembly,
 251 a thermal input parameter Q_v associated with the particles represents a new boundary condition for
 252 each conductive thermal time-step.

253 The expression for the mean temperature variation along the channel for a mean temperature
 254 $T_{m,out}$, in the case of constant channel surface T_s temperature, is derived from the energy balance
 255 for a control volume:

$$\frac{T_s - T_m(x)}{T_s - T_{m,i}} = e^{\left(-\frac{D_H x \bar{h}}{dm/dt} \right)} \quad (16)$$

256 where T_s is the channel surface temperature, $T_{m,i}$ is the mean fluid temperature at the channel
 257 entrance, $T_m(x)$ is the mean channel temperature at a position x , D_H is the channel hydraulic
 258 diameter ($D_H = 4A/p$], where A is the channel cross-sectional area and p is the wetted perimeter),
 259 dm/dt is the fluid mass flow rate through the channel cross-section at position x and \bar{h} is the
 260 average channel heat convection coefficient. The fluid mass flow rate is obtained from the pressure
 261 difference in the fluid channel. The average heat convection coefficient can be determined using
 262 the Nusselt number for a laminar flow for the parallel plate geometry ($N_{uD} = hD/k_f = 3.66$ for constant
 263 T_s) (Holman, 2002). A special case can occur when there is no local fluid flow through the fluid
 264 channel but fluid has different temperature than adjacent particle. The change of average particle
 265 i temperature with time is:

$$\frac{T_s - T_m(x)}{T_s - T_{m,i}} = e^{\left(\frac{dt}{\tau_t}\right)} \quad (17)$$

266 where T_∞ is the fluid temperature, $T_{i,0}$ is the particle temperature at the beginning of the time step,
 267 T_i is the particle temperature at the end of the time step, dt is the time step and τ_t is the thermal
 268 time constant:

$$\tau_t = \frac{\rho V c_p}{h A_s} \quad (18)$$

269 where ρ is the particle density, V is the particle volume, C_p is the particle material (rock) specific
 270 heat at a constant pressure, A_s is the surface of the contact and L is the length of the fluid channel.
 271 The value of the thermal time constant is a measure of how fast the temperature of the object reacts
 272 to its thermal environment. Eq. (17) is used to write a *FISH* function in PFC^{2D} for approximating
 273 the fluid temperature at the channel between two particles of each time step. If transient fluid flow
 274 is considered, some amount of energy storage will be included at each time t in the control volume
 275 of the fluid:

$$\frac{dQ_{st}}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt}(\rho V c_v T) \quad (19)$$

276 At each fluid domain, a control change in volume is assigned through the fluid flow *FISH* function.
 277 Accordingly, the conservation of energy can be written for a domain. The change in the domain
 278 thermal energy storage is equal to the heat flow rate from the adjacent channels minus the thermal
 279 energy of the domain at the beginning of the time-step:

$$\Delta Q_{dom} = Q_t - Q_{dom} \quad (20)$$

280 where Q_{dom} is the domain thermal energy, and Q_t is the convective heat transferred from the
 281 adjacent fluid channels.

282 The new particle temperature is imposed as a thermal boundary condition on enclosing
 283 particles for the next thermal time-step:

$$\Delta T = -\frac{dQ_{conv}}{c_{v,p} \rho_p V_p} \quad (21)$$

284 where ΔT is the particle temperature change, $dQ_{t,conv}$ is the amount of heat transferred from the
 285 particle to the fluid in the previous mechanical time-step, $c_{v,p}$ is the particle specific heat at constant
 286 volume, ρ_p is the particle density, and V_p is the particle volume.

287 An additional consideration is given to the case when fluid is present but there is no flow in a
288 fluid channel during the time-step and fluid has different temperature from the adjacent DEM
289 particles. Heat conduction still occurs at some extent between stagnant fluid and surrounding rock.
290 Lump capacitance method is used for determining the average particle heat change due to the
291 contact with stagnant fluid. The lumped capacitance method assumes uniform temperature over
292 entire particle, which is valid when the particle is very small, or the thermal conductivity of the
293 particle is very large. The validity of the lump capacitance method usage can also be determined
294 by inspecting the Biot number, which value must be $Bi < 0.1$.

$$Bi = \frac{hr}{k} \quad (22)$$

295 where h is the convective heat transfer coefficient between rock particle and surrounding fluid, r
296 is particle radius and k is rock heat conductivity. The Biot number in Eq. (22) uses the expression
297 for the plate with thickness L , and the simplification $L=r$ is introduced. The simplification for
298 observing the fluid flow channel between two particles as a small plate is justified because the
299 synthetic rock mass in DEM is discretized over spherical particles, where in fact they
300 mathematically still represent a continuum, i.e. the spaces between spheres are not open for fluid
301 flow.

302 **3. Results and Discussions**

303 Two-dimensional quadratic model of initially hot synthetic rock mass with the cold fluid
304 injection wellbore in the middle is used for studying HTM. This study focuses on investigating the
305 HTM deformation of continuum due to coupling with the fluid and heat flow from the wellbore in
306 permeable synthetic rock. Effect of synthetic rock deformation due to pressurizing fluid infiltration
307 and thermal effects on infiltration of fluid and heat is studied. Investigation interests include
308 conditions and occurrence of fingering instabilities in flow and their preferential directions in
309 biaxially compressed model. The fluid thermal expansion is not part of the study, and the
310 thermodynamic effect is not considered here. Therefore, the pore water compressibility is constant
311 as well as there is no volume change in pore water due to heating. Particles do change in volume
312 during cooling, which causes opening of preferential flow channels in the rock matrix. While the
313 water heating during infiltration into rock pores would cause an additional increase of the pore
314 pressure, the compressibility of the water slightly decreases at the same time. Therefore, the results

315 are conservative, since the additional pore pressure increase has not been considered. The
316 additional pore pressure increase would have increased the fingering effect.

317 The model dimensions, boundary and initial conditions are shown in Fig. 4. The model size is
318 $0.2 \times 0.2 \text{ m}^2$, with the DEM micro-mechanical parameters shown in Table 1. A synthetic granite
319 rock material is used in this study, and the resulting Bonded Particle Model macro-parameters are
320 given in Table 2. Bonded Particle Model for rock simulates continuum behavior, where the DEM
321 particles are cemented with parallel bonds with assigned stiffness and strength parameters. Initial
322 conditions for the synthetic rock sample are the initial homogeneous temperature field, $T_{ini}=200$
323 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and various biaxial confinement stresses at the sample boundaries for different problem runs.
324 The boundary conditions include constant temperature $T_{bound} = T_{ini} = 200 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the constant
325 boundary confinement stress during time stepping procedure at the four sides of the model. The
326 fifth model boundary is represented by the chain of particles around the hole in the middle of the
327 model. Initially, before the pressurized fluid applies additional thermal and mechanical stresses to
328 the synthetic rock around the hole, the temperature of the particles around the hole is equal to the
329 remaining rock, $T_{ini} = 200 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The initial stress state of the borehole boundary corresponds to the
330 self-affined stress field caused by creating the hole in the biaxially confined rock sample. DEM
331 particle temperatures are qualitatively plotted using a spectrum of 14 colors which represent
332 temperature ranges from $T = 50 - 200 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (blue to red), defined with a custom FISH function in
333 PFC^{2D}.

334 **3.1. Verification of the DEM model heat conduction solution**

335 Conductive heat flow in DEM model is verified with a numerical model using finite differences.
336 Fig. 5 shows conductive cooling of the synthetic and impermeable rock adjacent to the wellbore,
337 where the boundary conditions are set to $T_r = 200 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at the model four edges and $T_w = 50 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the
338 fluid in the wellbore. Three temporal snapshots $t_1 = 49.0 \text{ s}$, $t_2 = 245.1 \text{ s}$ and $t_3 = 490.2 \text{ s}$ is shown and
339 present the progress of transient radial cooling of the rock from the wellbore. The permeability of
340 the synthetic rock material in DEM is set to zero and kept constant, thus disabling the fluid flow
341 from the wellbore into the rock and convective heat flow and transport. The analytical solution for
342 heat flow and transport from the wellbore with convective boundary condition at the wellbore wall
343 between fluid and rock particles is discretized using finite differences and solved in Matlab and
344 shown in Fig. 6. A comparison of the results between DEM and finite difference model is shown
345 in Fig. 7. Agreement between results are generally satisfactory for the verification of conductive

346 DEM model. However, some discrepancies between the analytical and numerical solution exist
347 and are within 5%. The sources of error are spatial discretization of DEM compared to the
348 continuum approach in analytical solution. The conductive heat transfer in DEM occurs at particle
349 contacts which are randomly oriented, so the heat flow path can be slightly longer and random
350 compared to the direct path in analytical solution. Particle size directly affects the heat flow path,
351 and the offset can be corrected by better calibration of the DEM model thermal conductivity for
352 practical purposes.

353 For studying heat flow and transport from the wellbore in a spatially constrained model, it is
354 important to determine the location of the constant temperature boundary, which moves outwards
355 from the wellbore with time as rock changes temperature. The constant temperature boundary
356 denotes a location where the cooled rock around the wellbore and hot adjacent rock hold thermal
357 equilibrium. In a transient process and infinite spatial reservoir dimension, the cooling front
358 propagates from the wellbore with time if the thermal cooling flux is imposed at the wellbore. Fig.
359 8 shows results of the simulations for determining where to place the position of the heat boundary,
360 which is important for evaluation of the used modeling approach. It can be concluded that,
361 considering only the conductive heat flow through synthetic BPM rock matrix with zero
362 permeability, at the time of approximately $t=150-200$ s the heat boundary reaches the model edge
363 under pure conductive heat flow. To conclude, keeping the fixed boundary conditions in the
364 current model for larger times would not be realistic.

365 **3.2. Model permeability calculation**

366 Initial rock permeability of the synthetic rock is calibrated against published values for
367 Westerly Granite (Brace et al. 1968) by simulating the constant flow technique for testing low
368 permeability geomaterials in PFC^{2D} (Nakajima et al. 2007.; Olsen 1966). The tested rock sample
369 has dimensions of 5×5 cm². A constant flow rate was applied on the left boundary, and the
370 pressures difference across the model are recorded at prescribed times during the test. The final
371 pressure difference which is used for the permeability calculation is estimated following the test
372 convergence. Assuming the rock model is an isotropic medium, the compressibility between the
373 fluid and rock is neglected, and per Darcy's law, the steady state flow rate Q_{flow} is:

$$Q_{flow} = \frac{k_r H (P_{in} - P_{out})}{\mu W} \quad (23)$$

374 where k_r is the average macroscopic rock permeability, μ is the fluid dynamic viscosity, P_{in} and
375 P_{out} are left and right hand-side fluid pressures, H is the model height and W is the model width.
376 The permeability of the rock model is calculated as:

$$k_r = \frac{Q_{flow} \mu W}{H (P_{in} - P_{out})} \quad (24)$$

377 Fig. 9 shows results of the set of DEM simulations and relates the fluid flow channel aperture
378 in DEM models and the average model permeabilities measured on the 5 x 5 cm² synthetic rock
379 samples. The average permeability through the network of fluid flow channels is dictated with
380 both the particle size and assembly characteristics and the initial fluid channel aperture. Therefore,
381 the calibration results from the Fig. 10 correspond only to the model used in this study. The desired
382 granite permeability is chosen as a “target” range in Fig. 9 corresponding to those of Westerly
383 granite lab samples from the literature (Brace et al. 1968).

384 **3.3. Convective-conductive heat flow from the wellbore**

385 The convective-conductive heat flow and transport from the wellbore is introduced in the HTM
386 DEM model for better understanding the roles of heat convection and conduction in rock in EGS
387 reservoirs. Particularly, a hypothesis that heat convection can dominate over heat conduction in
388 rock around highly pressurized borehole is investigated. The Peclet number Pe number can be
389 calculated for a granite rock segment of 1.0 m, to evaluate fluid velocities relevant for the
390 convection dominance over the conduction. It is assumed that the fluid flows through the porous
391 rock of 1.0 m in length, where the granite rock has the following properties: $\lambda_r=3.07$ W/mK,
392 $C_p=0.79 \cdot 10^3$ J/kgK (Eppelbaum et al. 2014), water density is $\rho_w=1000$ kg/m³. Using Eq. (15), and
393 if $Pe \geq 1.0$ for convection to dominate and $Pe \gg 1.0$ for conduction to be completely negligible,
394 the fluid flow velocity needs to be larger than $v \geq 3.88 \cdot 10^{-6}$ m/s. Pe is estimated for each studied
395 case. Fluid velocity is calculated using the approximate average distance of the fluid flow and
396 cooled rock from the wellbore, as shown in the Table 3. In all cases the fluid velocities are $v \geq 3.88$
397 $\cdot 10^{-6}$ m/s, and that the convection dominates over conduction. Figs. 10 to 16 support this
398 calculation because the fluid infiltration can be seen accompanied with fluid heating in Figs. 10b
399 to 16b. In Figs. 10a to 16a it is evident that rock matrix DEM particles cool down rapidly as soon
400 as rock is subjected to contact with cold convected fluid, and the temperature gradient typical for
401 fluid conduction does not exist.

402 Prior to and during hydraulic fracturing, cold fluid injection increases pressure at a wellbore if
403 a constant fluid flow rate is applied. The heat exchange between hot rock and cold fluid occurs at
404 the wellbore walls via convection and conduction, where the heat is usually assumed to decrease
405 in rock mass around the wellbore via Fourier's law conduction. While the latter hypothesis may
406 be valid for impermeable solids, it is still not clear how the infiltration of cold fluid into permeable
407 rock mass combines its convective heat transport with the conduction of heat through solid rock
408 phase. The initial average permeability of synthetic granite is calibrated through initial aperture of
409 fluid channels, w_0 . The unconfined rock sample is modeled first and compared later with the
410 confined sample to isolate the effects of confinement stress contrast on heat flow and transport.
411 The boundary conditions of the unconfined rock sample are zero fluid flow, zero confinement
412 stress at sample outside boundaries and constant outside boundary temperature. For the confined
413 rock model, the biaxial confinement state of stress is imposed on the outside boundary, while all
414 other boundary conditions are the same as for the unconfined sample. The unconfined rock model
415 with initial and boundary temperature of $T_{ini} = T_r = 200$ °C is subjected to pressurized water at $T_w = 50$
416 °C from the wellbore.

417 Two unconfined rock sample with initial average permeability of $k = 1.91 \cdot 10^{-17}$ m² for two are
418 studied for different flow rates. Figs. 10 and 11 show results for case scenarios with $Q_1 = 0.06$ m³/s
419 and $Q_2 = 6.31$ m³/s constant flow rate over a small period of total time of $t = 5.55 \cdot 10^{-2}$ s. The rock
420 particles cooling and fluid flow reservoirs heating is visible around the wellbore through a particle
421 color change from hot (red) to cold (blue), using a 16-color scheme. The cooling rate of the rock
422 around the wellbore is clearly more pronounced in the case when higher fluid flow rate is applied
423 in Fig. 11. A band of blue particles (cold) is wider for the same time in Fig. 11 than in Fig. 10.
424 Thus, it is observed that the rock cooling rate is proportional to the rate of infiltration of colder
425 water into rock, via convection. If the trends in Figs. 10d or 11d are compared to Fig. 5, it can be
426 concluded that heat transported via convection is much faster than conduction itself in Fig. 5. Rock
427 particles around the wellbore are not nearly as cold after 40 s of conduction shown Fig. 5, as at the
428 time almost instantaneously during convective-conductive heat flow just shown in Fig. 11d,
429 without a significant heat gradient in the cooled region. Additionally, infiltrated fluid heats up due
430 to the heat exchange with adjacent rock particles and becomes warmer. Preferential fluid flow
431 paths form in the unconfined rock specimen and fluid infiltrates rock in a star-like fingers
432 formation. The fingering instabilities in heat flow and transport are caused by the preferential paths

433 occurrence. The preferential fluid paths form because of the faster cooling of rock adjacent to the
434 flow path compared to the rest of the rock. The local DEM particle cooling causes a slight decrease
435 of the particle diameter and therefore the increase of the adjacent fluid flow channel aperture.

436 Fig. 12 shows results for stepwise injection of cold fluid into hot rock, where the rock permeability
437 is relatively high for granite, with $k=1.91 \cdot 10^{-17} \text{ m}^2$ at a flow rate $Q_2=6.31 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. The stepwise
438 injection means that the wellbore is subjected to flow rate and pressures can drop for some time
439 before the next flow rate cycle. The maximum borehole pressure reached at the end of the
440 simulation is very low $P_b=1.89 \text{ kPa}$. Despite the low acting pressures and relatively short duration
441 of the injection, fluid gradually infiltrates rock and heats up as it flows away from the wellbore.
442 As a conclusion, not only the flow rate regime but also the wellbore pressure does not significantly
443 influence the rock cooling.

444 Biaxially confined model and convective-conductive heat flow and transport from the wellbore
445 is evaluated and results are shown in Figs. 13 to 16. The dominant direction of the cold fluid
446 infiltration and heat flow and transport in the direction parallel to minimum in situ confining stress.
447 Wellbore rock cooling is band shaped around the wellbore, where convection dominates
448 conduction with a negligible gradual cooling zone at the outer boundary of the cooling band of
449 particles. Higher flow rates cause faster wellbore pressure increase, but not necessarily faster
450 cooling of the rock. The pressure buildup in the wellbore is a product of constant flow rate pumping
451 and the elapsed time, without a significant pressure drop because of the small rock storage
452 coefficient. Storativity is included in the solution of the mass conservation equation for the
453 transient flow and transport using fluid flow channels and reservoirs. The rock cooling is also
454 observed around the wellbore, dominated by convection. The finger instabilities start to form also
455 in rock matrix. Fluid infiltration preferential path is more pronounced in Fig. 16 than in the
456 previous cases, because the time of the simulation is also larger. For example, in Fig. 14d the
457 wellbore pressure reached $P_b=216 \text{ MPa}$ after very short time, under continuous fluid flow rate.
458 Fluid pressure in the wellbore increases steadily in Figs. 14 and 15, reaching different maximum
459 values for the observed time. For example, in Fig. 13d after $t=0.063 \text{ s}$ the wellbore pressure reaches
460 $P_b=48,0 \text{ MPa}$ under $Q=0.67 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. Figs. 14a to 14d show a trend of simultaneous cooling of the
461 particles around the wellbore and fluid flow infiltration with fluid heating. Next, the fluid flow rate
462 is further decreased to $Q=0.0067 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, which is 100 times smaller than in Fig. 15. The wellbore
463 pressure reached only $P_b=0,56 \text{ MPa}$ after $t=0.108 \text{ s}$. However, the fluid infiltration and heating in

464 Fig. 15d looks very like the Fig. 14d regarding both the area of fluid infiltration in rock and fingers
 465 of fluid flow preferential paths direction. The cooled band of rock particles around the wellbore is
 466 a little bit smaller for lower flow rates in Fig. 15 than in Fig. 15. Fig. 16 shows the simulation with
 467 $Q=0.0011 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ for the maximum time of $t=3.05 \text{ s}$. In this case, the fluid pressure in the wellbore
 468 reached a maximum at $P_b=274,0 \text{ MPa}$, and is oscillating at high values.

469

470 3.3. Comparison of model results with advection-diffusion analytical solution

471 The analytical one-dimensional advection-diffusion equation is solved for heat flow and transport
 472 through porous rock and compared to the DEM model results. The verification is performed
 473 directly on the borehole models pressurized with cold water to evaluate the moving front of the
 474 hot rock cooling. Analytical solution does not consider the coupled hydro-mechanical effect into
 475 account, and the injected water thermal changes are not assumed. The one-dimensional advection-
 476 dispersion transport equation as found in Freeze and Cherry (1979) is used to verify the DEM
 477 model:

$$D_T \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial l^2} - v \frac{\partial T}{\partial l} = \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad (24)$$

478 where l is the coordinate along the flow path, v is the specific discharge or Darcy velocity, D_T is
 479 the thermal diffusivity coefficient, T is the temperature. A helpful analytical solution to the 1D
 480 advection-dispersion equation is given by Ogata and Banks (1961), and Ogata (1970):

$$\frac{T}{T_o} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{1-vt}{2\sqrt{D_T t}} \right) + \exp \left(\frac{vl}{D_T} \right) \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{1+vt}{2\sqrt{D_T t}} \right) \right] \quad (25)$$

481 where $\operatorname{erfc} \left((1+vt) / (2\sqrt{D_T t}) \right)$ is the complementary error function. Shackelford (1993) simplifies
 482 the above solution by making several dimensionless parameters and then plotting them in charts
 483 (Shackelford 1993). His version of the above solution is:

$$\frac{T}{T_o} = \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{1-S}{2\sqrt{\frac{S}{P}}} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \exp(P) \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{1+S}{2\sqrt{\frac{S}{P}}} \right) \quad (26)$$

484 where $S = vt / L$ and $P = vl / D_T$.

485 The average steady-state pore water velocity is estimated from the pressure difference at the
486 wellbore and the boundary, using the Darcy's law:

$$v = \frac{2\pi k(p_2 - p_1)}{\mu \ln(r_2 / r_1)} \quad (27)$$

487 Considering the seepage through the porous rock specimen, the fluid velocity is determined by
488 dividing the Darcy's velocity with the average estimated rock sample porosity:

$$v_s = \frac{v}{p_t} \quad (28)$$

489 where p_t is total rock porosity, with an average value for dense crystalline rocks $p_t=0.012$ taken for
490 the calculation. The thermal diffusivity coefficient for water is $D_T=1.43 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, and for granite
491 $D_T=8.49 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. The outer diameter r_2 is calculated using the same circumference as the square
492 DEM model, where $r_2=0.127 \text{ m}$ and $r_1=0.005 \text{ m}$. Fig. 17 shows results of rock heat flow and
493 transport calculation for the one-dimensional advection-dispersion heat transport from the
494 wellbore. The wellbore pressures are $P_{b,1}=0.56 \text{ MPa}$, $P_{b,1}=48.0 \text{ MPa}$ and $P_{b,1}=216.0 \text{ MPa}$. At
495 earlier times, when $t=1.0 \text{ s}$ the advective-diffusive calculation yields a thermal front not very far
496 from the wellbore, while after $t=10 \text{ s}$ the high-pressure calculation obtained distinct forward front
497 and the other two pressure cases follow. Thus, the moving front of the heat flow and transport in
498 analytical model depends on the pressure, keeping other parameters constant, which are the rock
499 permeability, the heat diffusion coefficient and the model geometry. Fig. 17 also shows results
500 from DEM models. The DEM models have stronger convection dominance which can be seen in
501 steeper curves and absence of temperature profile in the cooled rock region. Preferential flow paths
502 are formed in the DEM model, because of hydro-thermo-mechanical coupling and forming of local
503 higher permeability due to rock cooling.

504 Advective-diffusive analytical solution shows strong dependence on the wellbore pressure,
505 specially at later times. DEM model results do not show a strong cooling front penetration
506 dependence on borehole pressure buildup which is a result of low permeability and higher flow
507 rates. For example, the blue line represents Fig. 17 model, and although the time elapsed is the
508 largest and the borehole pressure is the largest of the three analyzed cases, the area of the cooled
509 rock around the wellbore is smallest. The flow rate is the smallest for the simulation in Fig. 17,
510 $Q=0.0011 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. The flow rate in Fig. 16 is $Q=0.0067 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and in Fig. 15 $Q=0.67 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. The high-
511 pressure buildup at the wellbore indicates poor fluid infiltration into the rock. Fig. 15 results are

512 show with orange line, and the cooling front is further from the wellbore wall. The flow rate in
513 Fig. 15 was the highest of three. Therefore, it is shown that when the HTM coupling is considered,
514 cooling of the rock depends on the flow rate at the borehole. Since the cooling of the rock and
515 moving of the cooled front depends on the rate at which the water in pores heats, there is an
516 additional negative effect when the flow rates are small and fluid velocities low.

517 Fig. 18 shows the cooling front distance measurement from DEM models for various flow
518 rates. The cooling distance front was chosen because of absence of visible temperature gradient.
519 Most of the cooled rock has temperature very similar to the injected cold water colored in blue. It
520 can be seen from Figs. 18a and b that there is no linear relationship between flow rate and cooling
521 rate of the rock, although a trend of general cooling rate decrease is shown as the flow rate rises
522 towards higher values. For highest flow rates, the cooling front is not much further than at lower
523 flow rates. The result indicates importance of HTM coupled processes, where the rock
524 permeability largely dictates the rock cooling rate, but as well the fluid heating during flow through
525 hot rock contributes to the retardation of the cooling front advancement. Fig. 19 plots all the DEM
526 results from Figs. 10 to 16 without the Fig. 11, where the recorded time was used to calculate the
527 average moving front velocity.

528 **4. Conclusions**

529 This study numerically investigated the hydro-thermo-mechanical (HTM) coupled processes of
530 fluid and heat flow and transport in intact low permeability rock. The study used the Discrete
531 Element Method (DEM) coupled with numerical scheme of heat and fluid flow and transport via
532 a system of pores and channels, which are superimposed to the DEM synthetic rock matrix. Initial
533 model permeability was calibrated towards a low permeability intact crystalline rock, as well as,
534 rock matrix mechanical parameters. The study was aimed at contributing to the better
535 understanding of how cold fluid infiltrates hot dry rock matrix under high stress and high
536 temperature conditions typical for deep geothermal reservoirs.

537 Although much effort has been devoted towards modeling of coupled processes in rock at a
538 reservoir-scale, coupled HTM behavior of rock is not well understood from micro-mechanical
539 perspective. This study shows how altering the near-wellbore region occurs in terms of spatial and
540 temporal rock permeability evolution. HTM coupled processes exhibit fingering instabilities at a
541 microscale driven by convective-conductive fluid and heat flow and transport. Since we have
542 observed major rock cooling caused by convection, rock microcracks can develop quickly and

543 locally. Thermally caused damage in rock around the wellbore at small times can be crucial for
544 fracture initiation and propagation. Effects of varying flow rate magnitude and regime as stepwise
545 or continuously increasing pressure on convective-conductive heat flow and transport are
546 evaluated in this study. Absolute magnitude of injection pressure effect on heat and fluid flow and
547 transport during infiltration in rock is also investigated. Results show that despite the low acting
548 pressures at early times, fluid instantly infiltrates into adjacent rock and gradually heats up as it
549 flows away from the injection point at a wellbore. Heat exchange between fluid and rock occurs
550 and rock around the wellbore cools down. Cooling of the rock is dominated by convective heat
551 transport via moving fluid. Conductive heat flow and transport through the rock matrix is
552 negligible in this case. A comparison with equivalent analytical solution of conductive heat flow
553 and transport shows that timeframe for conduction is several times of magnitude higher than what
554 is needed for heat to be transported by convection. Novel micro-mechanical understanding of
555 convective heat and transport dominance over conduction is significant for large-scale modeling
556 where conduction is assumed to be dominant process. It is observed in all the modeling results that
557 fluid infiltration occurs through preferential paths. HTM coupling causes local permeability changes
558 driven by local deformation because of rock matrix cooling. The observed instability phenomenon
559 is very similar to development of fingering instability during infiltration of chemically active fluid
560 as it locally dissolves rock matrix causing preferential paths to develop. The micromechanical
561 study indicates that the simple advection-diffusion equation under predicts the cooling front
562 advancement from the wellbore. In the unconfined rock sample, the preferential fluid paths
563 develop in a star-like formation. On the contrary, in the biaxially confined sample preferential fluid
564 paths are longer in the direction of the minimum in situ compressive stress. Despite instabilities,
565 the general direction of fluid infiltration and rock cooling is influenced by in-situ stress regime.
566 More importantly, the preferred direction would not coincide with the direction of hydraulic
567 fracture propagation in the reservoir, which develops in a plane perpendicular to the minimum in-
568 situ confining stress direction. Fluid wellbore pressure was found to be irrelevant for the rock
569 cooling. The speed and distance of the cooling front trend ceases for increased fluid flow rates,
570 where it approaches asymptotically some maximum value. Continuous and stepwise flow rates
571 regimes yielded similar results, indicating that the regime of pumping is also not very relevant for
572 rock cooling. However, it was observed that the rock cooling rate is directly related to the rate of
573 infiltration of colder water into rock. To clarify, rock limited permeability, fluid flow path widths,

574 along with fluid properties, dictates the rock capacity for fluid infiltration. The capacity of rock to
575 accept a certain amount of fluid is limited by its permeability and it is not sensitive to pressure in
576 the wellbore, if there are no new cracks forming.

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674 **Tables:**

675 Table 1. Micro-mechanical properties of BPM, R_{min} = minimum particle radius; R_{max} = maximum particle radius; $f\bar{i}$ =
 676 particle friction coefficient; P_{b_kn} = parallel bond normal stiffness; P_{b_ks} = parallel bond shear stiffness; P_{b_sstr} = parallel
 677 bond shear strength; P_{b_nstr} = parallel bond normal strength; and w_0 = initial fluid channel aperture.

Parameter	Value
R_{min} (mm)	0.1
R_{max}/R_{min} (-)	1.66
$f\bar{i}$ (-)	0.2
P_{b_kn} (GPa)	7.0
P_{b_ks} (GPa)	2.8
P_{b_sstr} (MPa)	>>21.4
P_{b_nstr} (MPa)	>>4.9
w_0 (m)	$10^{-4}/10^{-5}$
x (cm)	20.0
y (cm)	20.0

678
 679 Table 2. Macro-mechanical properties of BPM compared to the average granite.

	Tensile Strength	Young's Modulus	Fracture Toughness	Poisson's Ratio
	σ_t (MPa)	E (GPa)	K_{IC} (MPa \sqrt{m})	ν (-)
PFC ^{2D}	4.37	57.7	0.31	0.21
Granite	3-25	30-70	0.11-0.41	0.25

680
 681 Table 3. Fluid velocities in permeable DEM rock matrix calculated in Figs. 11 to 17.
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Figure number	Fluid velocity v (m/s)
11	0.18
12	0.25
13	0.015
14	1.11
15	0.79
16	0.185
17	0.0065

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Figure 1. System of thermal pipes for conductive heat flow in Bonded Particle Model (BPM).

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Figure 2. Bonded Particle Model (BPM) with fluid flow channels and reservoirs.

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Figure 3. Axial temperature variation for a convective heat transfer in a channel. The convective heat is transported with fluid along the fluid flow channel.

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711 Figure 4. DEM model with initial and boundary conditions, where T_r is the rock temperature and
712 T_w is the wellbore temperature.
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714 a) $t=49.0\text{ s}$ b) $t=245.1\text{ s}$ c) $t=490.2\text{ s}$
715 Figure 5. Heat flow from the wellbore in impermeable synthetic rock sample, where the DEM
716 time step is $\Delta t=0.49\text{ s}$.
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Figure 6. Heat flow from the wellbore modeled using finite differences.

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Figure 7. A comparison of the Finite Difference Solution and Discrete Element model for heat conduction in rock model from the borehole.

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Figure 8. Heat boundary for the conductive heat flow from the borehole.

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Figure 9. The numerical relationship between the initial average synthetic rock permeability and the model parameter of initial fluid flow channel.

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Figure 10. Conductive-convective heat flow and transport in the unconfined model, where $k=1.91 \cdot 10^{-17} \text{ m}^2$ and the flow rate is $Q_I=0.06 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, times are a) $t_1=7.93 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ s}$; b) $t_2=2.38 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ s}$, c) $t_3=3.96 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ s}$, and d) $t_4=5.55 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ s}$.

739 Figure 11. Conductive-convective heat flow and transport in the unconfined model, where
 740 $k=1.91 \cdot 10^{-17} \text{ m}^2$, where the flow rate is $Q_2=6.31 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, times are a) $t_1=7.93 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ s}$; b) $t_2=2.38 \cdot 10^{-2}$
 741 s, c) $t_3=3.96 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ s}$, and d) $t_4=5.55 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ s}$.

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 743 Figure 12. Conductive-convective heat flow and transport in the confined model, where
 744 $k=1.91 \cdot 10^{-17} \text{ m}^2$ and the flow rate $\Delta V=10^{-5}$ is limited to reach lower max pressures and repeated
 745 in steps time-steps are a) $9.95 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ s}$; b) 0.227 s; c) 0.4 s; and d) 0.63 s.
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747 Figure 13. Conductive-convective heat flow and transport in the confined model, where
 748 $k=1.91 \cdot 10^{-17} \text{ m}^2$ and the flow rate $Q = 5.0 \text{ ml/min}$, time-steps are a) $4.27 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ s}$; b) $7.27 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ s}$; c)
 749 $1.04 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ s}$; and d) $1.35 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ s}$.

750 Figure 14. Conductive-convective heat flow and transport in the confined model, where
 751 $k=1.91 \cdot 10^{-17} \text{ m}^2$, where the flow rate $Q=0.67 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ ($\Delta V = 10^{-7}$), time-steps are a) 0.017 s ; b) 0.033
 752 s ; c) 0.047 s ; and d) 0.063 s .

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754 Figure 15. Conductive-convective heat flow and transport in the confined model, where
 755 $k=1.91 \cdot 10^{-17} \text{ m}^2$, where the flow rate $Q=0.0067 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ ($\Delta V=10^{-9}$), time-steps are a) 0.017 s; b)
 756 0.047 s; c) 0.063 s; and d) 0.108 s.

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758 Figure 16. Conductive-convective heat flow and transport in the confined model, where
 759 $k=1.91 \cdot 10^{-17} \text{ m}^2$, where the flow rate $Q=0.0011 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ ($\Delta V=16.5 \cdot 10^{-10}$), time-steps are a) 0.15 s; b)
 760 0.9 s; c) 1.5 s; and d) 3.05 s.

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763 Figure 17. One-dimensional advection-diffusion solution for the heat flow and transport from the
764 wellbore.

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767 a) Figure 18. (a) Cooling front distance from the wellbore and (b) speed as a function of fluid
768 injection flow rate at the wellbore

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771 Figure 19. Cooling front distance from the wellbore as a function of fluid volume injected at the
 772 wellbore for all DEM steps

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